

Adoption of Digital Marketing Techniques: A Survey of Marketing Executives in Pune

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CITATION: Darekar, Sheetal M.; Wadajkar, Vishal and Ejaj, Adil (2019), "Adoption of Digital Marketing Techniques: A Survey of Marketing Executives in Pune", *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 7, Special Issue 2, pp. 11-14.

ARTICLE HISTORY: Submitted: April 01, 2019, Revision received: April 18, 2019, Accepted: April 30, 2019

ARTICLE TYPE: Research paper

ABSTRACT

This is a descriptive study to assess the adoption of digital marketing techniques using a survey questionnaire. An explanatory hypothesis was set and studied based on primary data collected from 100 senior marketing executives from Pune. Different companies surveyed them on the adoption of digital marketing techniques. The responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale for ten sub-questions. The sample mean was compared against the hypothesised population mean of the scale mid-point of 2 and was tested for statistical significance at a 95% confidence level. The study disclosed that the adoption of digital marketing techniques was statistically significant. The mean was well above the hypothesised population mean (Mean = 3.13; SD = 0.79). The results of the study indicates that the adoption of digital marketing techniques is widely prevalent.

KEYWORDS: Digital marketing, internet, social media.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital is at the core of everything in marketing today - it has gone from 'one of the things marketing does' to 'THE thing that marketing does'. At a high level, digital marketing alludes to advertising conveyed through digital channels, for example, search engines, websites, social media, email, and mobile apps.

Utilising these online media channels, digital marketing is the technique by which organisations support goods, services, and brands. Consumers intensely depend on digital intends to research items. For instance, Google marketing experiences found that 48% of consumers start their requests on search engines, while 33% look to brand websites and 26% search inside mobile applications.

There are various channels for digital marketing such as – paid search, search engine optimisation, content marketing, social media marketing, email marketing, mobile marketing, and marketing automation. By executing an Omnichannel digital marketing methodology, marketers can gather meaningful experiences into target crowd practices while making way for new strategies for client commitment.

Moreover, organisations can hope to see an expansion in retention. As per a report, organisations with solid Omnichannel client commitment techniques hold a normal of 89% of their clients contrasted with organisations with weak Omnichannel programs that have a standard for the dependability of simply 33%. Given the growing importance of digital marketing, we decided to survey senior marketing executives from Pune from different companies on digital marketing techniques.

1.1 The research question to be addressed is as follows:

RQ: Is there a reasonable adoption of digital marketing techniques among senior marketing executives in Pune, India?

The term “reasonable” was operationalised at the mid-point of a 5-point Likert scale at the value of $(0+1+2+3+4)/5=2$, with 0 indicating Not at all used and four indicating widely used.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

We are in the digital era, and internet marketing and social media significantly affect how customers carry on; organisations work together; what's more, it is an absolute necessity for organisations to adjust to the new reality. Even though the new era of communication is here, organisations ought not overlook traditional methods and attempt to mix digital marketing with conventional missions to accomplish their objectives (Todor, 2016).

This examination by Yoga *et al.* (2019) pointed toward investigating the use of information technology, especially in computerised channels of advertising correspondence, for example, websites and social media. The primary spotlight is on different organisations utilising information technology media to assemble brand familiarity with their administrations and pulling in their potential objective market. This exploration targets how advertisers know and use information technology to convey their business exercises while facing various barriers to realise and process data.

The investigation by Alghizzawi (2019) audits the role digital marketing plays on consumer behaviour through three measurements: (1) mobile apps, (2) social media platforms, and (3) electronic word-of-mouth. The principal point of this investigation is to reveal insight into the role digital marketing plays in consumer behaviour. The assessed writing demonstrated the significance of digital correspondence on consumer behaviour and their utilisation of social media and mobile applications.

At present, the digital economy contributes conclusively to an expansion in competitiveness, particularly as a digital transformation includes moving to new technological models where digital marketing is a critical piece of growth and user loyalty strategies. Internet and Digital Marketing have become significant variables in missions, which pull in and hold Internet users. This examination expects to distinguish the primary ways users can be picked up and carried by utilising Digital Marketing. The aftereffects of the exploration recognise the particular activities that should be completed to draw in and hold users in B2C organisations that use the Digital Marketing system on the Internet (Lopez Garcia *et al.*, (2019)).

A contextual research gap exists, and hence this study was undertaken by surveying senior marketing professionals.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology adopted is outlined below:

1. A survey questionnaire was administered to 100 (Bullen, 2016) senior marketing executives.
2. The selection of the 100 senior marketing executives was based on the writer's judgment of getting an adequate response in a reasonable time. Convenient sampling was used.
3. The survey questionnaire had ten questions related to the adoption of digital marketing techniques.
4. Responses were sought on a 5-point Likert scale.
5. To assess the adoption of digital marketing techniques, the scale used was: 0-Not at all used, 1-Used a little bit, 2-Used somewhat, 3-Used well, 4-Used widely. The ten sub-questions were: 1 - the combination of marketing techniques, 2 - internet, 3 – mobile devices, 4 – social media, 5 – content marketing, 6 – email, 7 – paid search, 8 – SEO, 9- marketing automation and 10 – interactive marketing.

4. STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESIS

1. Ho1: The level of adoption of digital marketing techniques is reasonable
2. Ha1: The level of adoption of digital marketing techniques is better than reasonable

Data analysis included descriptive analysis specifying features of the sample and inferential analysis to test the hypothesis. A t-test was used because the SD of the population is not known, in which case, a Z-test could have been applied.

A t-test in practice is widely used as a substitute for the Z-test wherein the SD of the sample is taken as the SD of the population (given unknown population SD). The survey instrument returned a Cronbach's alpha of 0.88, which is better than 0.70 (the standard) and hence was considered reliable.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Descriptive analysis

79 out of the 100 senior marketing executive respondents surveyed were male, while 21 were female. Twenty-six marketing professionals belonged to the age group <40 years, 35 were from the age-group 40-50, while 39 were from the age group >50 years. Twenty-five marketing professionals reported work experience in the range of 10-15 years, 34 in the range of 15-20 years, and 41 had work experience of more than 20 years. Forty-two respondents were from the manufacturing sector, while 58 were from the service sector.

5.2 Inferential analysis

The null hypothesis was set as the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) equals the hypothesised population mean (μ). The alternate hypothesis was: $H_1: \bar{x} > 2$. This was set based on the common knowledge that day-by-day digital marketing techniques are gaining traction. Summary of the ratings for the adoption of digital marketing are given in Table 1 below:

Concepts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average adoption rating	3.26	3.18	3.08	3.07	3.22	3.08	3.1	3.1	3.2	3.02	3.13

Table 2 shows the testing of the hypothesis at a 95% confidence level.

Parameter	H1 value
Sample Mean ($\bar{x}$)	3.13
Hypothesised population mean (μ)	2.00
SD of sample	0.79
n (sample size)	100
t-value= $\text{abs}((\bar{x} - \mu) / (s/\sqrt{n}))$	14.40
p-value = $\text{tdist}(t, (n-1), 1)$	0.00000
Decision	Reject Null

The null hypothesis was rejected, favouring the alternate that the sample mean is significantly different from the hypothesised population mean.

5.3 Discussion on results

The sample mean for the adoption of digital marketing techniques was 3.13 (SD = 0.79) on a maximum scale of 4 and was significantly higher than a reasonable level assumed at the mid-point of the scale, that is, 2.

6. CONCLUSION

The research shows that the adoption of digital marketing techniques is significant. These techniques are day by day gaining popularity and are inevitably part of the marketing tools. Internet penetration has enabled the usage of digital marketing techniques, and product or service providers are finding it effective. Moreover, there are different digital marketing techniques, and marketers are using a combination of them. As the study was based on sampling, limitations of sampling, in general, apply to it as well. Researchers are encouraged to study specific digital marketing techniques, which will add to the earlier research.

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